

8T – The $\dot{V}$ Operator

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Abstract:

By analyzing the relation between the three components – mass momenta and velocity, the author will present an 8T analog, that is correlating mass to curvature converging and momenta to curvature diverging, to reach the velocity analog as presented in Quantum mechanics.

Introduction

The 8T is a the theory of variational curvature, the main equation (1) is describing the principle of equivalence between gravity and acceleration, and by demanding the two conditions $\partial g / \partial t = 0$ and $\frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$ we have the conditions to "dark energy" which Is the result of distinct manifolds interacting in areas of extremum curvatures.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.42) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.4)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (1.41)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.42)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term of equation (1) and derived the existence of Fermions. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matrix tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

The wave equation of the Bosonic class is represented by the wave equation, which is net curvature diverging on the matric tensor. that is by a five-vector.

$$\left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3)_\mu\right) + N_{V\mu} \rightarrow \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_{V\mu} + (e)_\mu\right) + N_{V\mu}$$

$$\mu = (\nabla^2, t_n, s_n)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t_n^2} N_V = \nabla^2 N_V \quad (1.33)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial t_n^2} = \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial z^2}$$

The key point to take from this is the following – the curvature ripple is the momenta as presented in Quantum mechanics.

$$M\dot{V} = -\nabla U$$

$$U = (X, Y, Z)$$

We can also instantly see that the mass is inversely proportional to the velocity. In the 8T, the mass is considered curvature converging represented by the Quark masses series, that is by 8 – (1) variations, which allowed to the derive the pattern of total masses decreasing:

$$19,600 \rightarrow 1400 \rightarrow 56$$

$$176,400 \rightarrow 1400 \rightarrow 6.3 \rightarrow 0.113 \rightarrow$$

By the primorial, the series of diverging net curvature unbound is represented by terms which are of the sort of 8 + (1) for the first, and scalar multiples of that 8 + (1) and additional prime for the higher coupling term. The key point is the following. The velocity operator is than represented by the relation of

$$\dot{V} = \frac{8 + (1)}{8 - (1)} = -\frac{\nabla U}{M}$$

In the 8T thesis, there is an analog to this relation by the Einstein equation between mass and energy. Energy is represented as the curvature diverging, and the mass as the curvature converging, the following ratio has a root which is the speed of light.

$$8 - (1) \rightarrow \mathcal{G}_c$$

$$8 + (1) \rightarrow \mathcal{G}_d$$

Curvature diverging $\mathcal{G}_d$ is equal to curvature converging, $\mathcal{G}_c$, times the square of speed of light. A new version of the Einstein equation, equation 5.1).

$$\mathcal{G}_d = \mathcal{G}_c c^2 \quad (5.1)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

M. Ohad's Theory

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